

ABSTRACT OF THE PROJECT¹ FROM OHBM BRAINHACK (HACKATHON 2017)

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Title: Region(s) of interest (ROI's) based analysis of schizophrenic brain using fMRI data.

Rationale: Region(s) of Interest (ROI) - based analysis has been used as a method for data analysis focusing on some particular areas of interest to inspect the structural and functional changes in a predefined region(s). Schizophrenia is a serious mental disorder which is still not completely recoverable. It affects different regions of the brain which subsequently causes hallucination and delusion. Currently, schizophrenia is diagnosed on clinical analysis which is prone to error and subjective in nature. Localization of affected regions in schizophrenia may help us understand the condition and effect of disorder better and may also assist in deciding the line of treatment. This project may throw some light on the region-wise analysis and their individual working condition in the brain having schizophrenia.

The objective of the Project:

- 1) ROI study of the affected brain in schizophrenia using fMRI data to investigate the functional changes in each region.
- 2) Identification of the most affected region(s) in Schizophrenia
- 3) To develop a decision model using Multi-objective optimization evolutionary approach.

The Plan of Work: In this project, we use fMRI data of schizophrenia patients and healthy controls performing Auditory Oddball task, openly available from FBIRN phase II data repository. We extract different regions from brain atlases and investigate the regions most affected by the disorder. We use machine learning algorithms to train the classification model. Multi-objective optimization technique using an evolutionary approach will be used to improve the criteria for voxel selection within the search space. Tools like Matlab, SPM8, MriCro, and MANGO will be used here to implement the project.

¹ This project was performed at the OHBM Brainhack 2017, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada, during June 22-24, 2017.